

HEATING OF CONTINUOUS-FIBRE-REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC LAMINATES PRIOR TO THERMOFORMING

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ABSTRACT

The processing of continuous fibre-reinforced thermoplastics in an industrial scale is a subject attracting considerable attention in the last years. Beside the optimization of the mechanical properties and of the process parameters, an investigation of the economic aspects is also necessary. A forming technique with economic advantages is thermoforming in a press, with an external appliance to heat the laminates up to the required forming temperature. The most important factors influencing the economic efficiency of the process are the heating and cooling times. A comparison between the commonly used preheating techniques, i.e. circulating-air oven, infrared (radiation) heating, contact heating, is presented, and the problems inherent to each technique discussed. It is shown that a fast and consequently economical preheating is possible without damaging the laminate. The material also possesses a high heat capacity which enables a sufficiently high temperature to be maintained, despite the heat losses during transport from the heating station to the press. The recorded heating and cooling rates at various preheating temperatures are compared with the results obtained by computation and show a good agreement. It is shown that application of the computational method can simplify the optimization process considerably and provide a forecast on the economic efficiency of the thermoforming process for a variety of materials.

Keywords: Continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastics processing, heating, cycle times.

1. INTRODUCTION

Compared to thermosetting materials continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastics require very short production times for their processing and manufacture into parts. With the thermoforming of preheated laminates in tempered moulds or at room temperature, forming times of a few seconds and total cycle times (positioning-forming-demoulding) of down to 30 seconds are realistic. For example a glassfibre-reinforced PETP requires a total press time (moulding and cooling) of 15 to 60 seconds depending on the thickness of the laminate /1/. A carbonfibre-reinforced PP requires 15 seconds /2/. The cooling time (time interval between forming and demoulding) depends on the matrix material, the laminate thickness, the mould temperature and the desired demoulding temperature. A necessary condition for a constant manufacturing quality with thermoforming is that a uniformly preheated and damage-free laminate be brought to the mould.

2. PROCESSING OF CONTINUOUS FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

The following manufacturing stages provide an example of an economic thermoforming process for continuous-fibre-reinforced thermoplastics, Figure 1

Figure 1. Processing stations for fibre reinforced thermoplastics

1. Supply of consolidated laminates with fibre and matrix material, fibre direction, fibre content and laminate thickness adapted to the requirements of the part to be produced
2. Cutting of laminates to the required shape
3. Loading the laminate on a supporting frame in order to transfer it to the heating station and subsequently to the mould
4. Transferring the laminate to the heating station
5. Heating to a sufficiently high temperature, in order to ensure that the laminate is at the desired forming temperature after having taken into account the heat loss during transfer
6. Transferring the laminate to the forming equipment
7. Forming and subsequent cooling of the part in the closed mould
8. Demoulding

3. HEATING

3.1 Heating Requirements

The heating process must meet the following requirements:

1. Uniform heating of the whole surface of the laminate
2. Heating must take place without causing any damage due to
 - local overheating
 - too long heatingtimes, through too slow heat exchange
3. The heating must be an economic process, and therefore the following factors are of importance:
 - the investment costs of the equipment
 - the dwell time of each laminate in the heating station
 - the operating costs (energy costs) assigned to the heated laminate

3.2 Heating Methods

The following heating methods are investigated in this paper

- contact heating
- infrared (radiation) heating
- circulating-air oven

3.2.1 Contact Heating

In contact heating, heated metal plates are laid on one or preferably on both surfaces of the laminate. The plates may be heated electrically or by other means. The uniformity of the temperature distribution on the laminate surface depends on the temperature distribution on the surface of the heating plate itself, provided that good contact between laminate and plate over the whole surface area is ensured. Problems associated with the method are due to sticking of the soft matrix on the heating surfaces, which has been observed in many thermoplastics. The application of release agents to the surfaces of the plates may inhibit subsequent joining operations like welding or adhesion. Release agent residues must be removed prior to the joining operation. Even the low pressure which must be applied to the heating plates in order to ensure a good heat transfer can cause, as soon as the material is softened, flow of the matrix, leading to an undesirable loss of matrix. A further problem is the tackiness of the softened thermoplastics, which impedes the removal of the laminate from the heating plates. With some thermoplastics an improvement can be achieved by introducing an interleaving foil between laminate and heating plate. A further improvement can be achieved by shock-cooling of the laminate surface /3/.

3.2.2 Infrared Heating

In this case the laminate is heated free of contact by means of infrared radiation. The radiation energy will be conveyed to the laminate surface, the penetration depth is depending on the wavelength and the matrix material. The penetration depth is limited by the presence of the fibres and is very small compared to the laminate thickness. The heating of the inside takes place by heat conduction from the surface layer. This method is capable of very short preheating times. The uniformity of the temperature distribution depends on the temperature profile of the radiating elements as well as on the uniformity of the absorption behaviour of the laminate surface.

3.2.3 Circulating-Air Oven

In a circulating-air oven warm air flows around the laminate. Heating is relatively slow because the heat must be transferred from the air to the laminate. The amount of heat being transferred to the laminate can be increased by increasing the flow velocity (impingement heating). The advantage of this method is a very uniform heating without local overheating. The slow heating can be compensated by preheating the laminates in batches rather than singly. A circulating-air oven can be conveyORIZED in order to enable a continuous operation.

4. HEAT TRANSFER

The derivation of the following equation is useful for the computation of the dwell time in the heating station, which is necessary in order to ensure adequate preheating and in order to compensate for the heat losses during transport to the mold. A heat transfer due to convection and radiation are considered.

A convective heat flow into a body can be expressed as

$$\dot{q}_{conv} = \alpha(T) \cdot (T_{\infty} - T) \quad (1)$$

where \dot{q}_{conv} is the heat flow per unit area in W/m²
 $\alpha(T)$ the heat-convection constant in W/m²K
 T_{∞} the heater temperature in K
 T the body's temperature in K

The amount q of heat per unit mass transferred to the laminate and its temperature change from T to the heater temperature T_∞ are related by

$$q = c_p \cdot (T_\infty - T) \quad (2)$$

where c_p is the specific heat capacity in J/kgK

The radiation heat transfer per unit area from the heater at a temperature T_∞ to the laminate at T is given by the Stefan Boltzmann law

$$\dot{q}_{rad} = \epsilon \cdot \sigma \cdot (T_\infty^4 - T^4) \quad (3)$$

where ϵ is the emission coefficient of the laminate (measured)
 σ the Stefan Boltzmann constant

Integrating these equations for a plate of thickness d , adding the contributions from convection and radiation and assuming the density and the specific heat capacity to be constant within a small temperature interval gives

$$t_2 - t_1 = \frac{d}{2} \cdot c_p(T) \cdot \rho(T) \int_{T_1}^{T_2} \frac{dT}{\alpha(T) \cdot (T - T_\infty) + \epsilon \sigma \cdot (T^4 - T_\infty^4)} \quad (4)$$

This is the integration over a temperature interval T_1 to T_2 . The curve in Figure 4 is obtained by adding the time intervals $t_1 - t_2$ calculated in eq. (4) for the temperature range in the laminate, from room temperature to the required removal temperature.

The heat-convection constant may be defined in terms of the Nusselt relation

$$\alpha(T) = Nu(T) \frac{\lambda(T)}{l} \quad (5)$$

where λ is the heat-conduction coefficient in W/mK
 l the plate length in m

The calculation of the temperature dependent heat-convection coefficient $\alpha(T)$ can be performed with the aid of a suitable Nusselt relation. Because the oven manufacturer has given a maximum flow velocity of 1 m/s the case can be approximately treated as free convection.

The Nusselt relation for a vertical plate is given by

$$Nu(T) = \left[0.825 + 0.387 \cdot (Gr(T) \cdot Pr(T) \cdot 0.345)^{\frac{1}{6}} \right]^2 \quad (6)$$

where $Gr(T)$ is the Grashof's number
 $Pr(T)$ the Prandtl's number of air ($Pr = 0.71$)
 $\beta(T)$ the coefficient of thermal expansion of air in 1/K
 $\nu(T)$ the kinematic viscosity of air in m^2/s
 g the standard acceleration due to gravity in m/s^2

$$Gr(T) = g \cdot l^3 \frac{\beta(T)}{\nu(T)^2} \cdot (T - T_\infty) \quad (7)$$

For a horizontal plate

$$Nu_{horizontal} = 0.8307 \cdot Nu_{vertical} \quad (8)$$

Figure 2. Numerical integration

The integration of Equation (4) is performed numerically as follows:

1. Definition of the material constants of the air
2. Definition of the material constants of the laminate and of the geometry
3. Definition of the heater temperature and of the removal temperature
4. Integration step 1: Computation of the laminate temperature in first approximation and determination of the new material constants
- Integration step 2: Computation of the laminate temperature in second approximation and determination of the new material constants
5. Adaption of time interval: reduction of the time interval if c_p changes markedly
6. Repetition of steps 4 and 5 until the desired temperature is reached.

The heating rate inside the laminate depends on the surface temperature. The higher the surface temperature of the laminate, the faster the heating rate. In circulating-air ovens and radiation heaters the surface temperature can be increased by increasing the oven and the radiation temperature respectively. In convection heating, however, the heat transfer to the surface of the laminate depends also on the flow velocity. In the case of radiation heating the danger of overheating arises if the dwell time in the radiation field is too long. On the other hand in a convection oven the temperature of the laminate cannot exceed the oven temperature. Accordingly a rapid heating method is proposed, which comprises a convection oven, the temperature of which is adjusted to a value considerably higher than the melting point of the thermoplastic material, however not so high as to cause any thermal damage. Due to the temperature difference between the laminate on the one side and the air and oven wall on the other side, a great amount of heat enters the laminate when starting the heating and therefore a fast heating rate is achieved without the danger of overheating. The heat transfer is additionally supported by convection.

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In order to investigate the various possibilities for preheating and also as experimental verification of the theoretical considerations, tests were performed, using 2 mm thick laminates with thermocouples embedded halfway through the laminate's thickness.

Figure 3 shows the comparison between contact, convection and radiation heating of GF/PA 6 laminates. The heating plates and the oven were at the same temperature of 260°C, whereas the radiation heater had to be adjusted to 305°C in order to produce the same end temperature in the laminate as in the other two heating methods. The diagram shows that heating between the plates takes place very rapidly. After 30 seconds, the final temperature had been already reached. In the circulating-air oven and the radiation heater the same temperature was reached after 4 and 5 minutes respectively. A fast preheating of the 2 mm material is therefore not a question of the heat transfer from the surface to the interior of the laminate but one concerning the heat transfer from the heat source to the laminate surface.

Figure 3. Time-temperature curves, comparison of heating systems, laminate 2 mm GF/PA6

By increasing the oven temperature to 400°C a laminate temperature of 250°C was reached after only 60 seconds.

Figure 4. Heating in circulating-air oven, computation and measurement, laminate 2 mm GF/PA12

Figure 4 shows a comparison between calculated laminate heating times in the oven, using the theory above, and those measured by the thermocouples. There is a good agreement between theory and experiment.

For the heating tests, a laboratory circulating-air oven with a large door was used. The opening of this door to insert the laminate to be heated caused a temperature decrease in the oven, shown in the small diagram in Figure 4. This temperature decrease is shown for 300 and 400°C nominal oven temperature.

This behaviour causes a delayed temperature increase of the laminate, see measured curve and calculated values in Figure 4. With circulating-air ovens used in production, loading and removal of the laminates can be done in such a way that no essential decrease in oven temperature occurs and heating of the laminates will follow the values calculated without temperature decrease.

An increase in the temperature of the infrared heater also results in a considerable decrease of the preheating time. With an IR-heater temperature of 600°C a laminate temperature of 250°C was reached in less than 40 seconds.

Short heating times, similar to those achieved by contact heating, are thus possible in the case of convection and radiation heating. However, prior to applying these techniques, the possibility of thermal damage caused by a heat source adjusted to a higher temperature must be investigated.

Two kinds of thermal damage are possible:

- The laminate remains too long at a high temperature, e.g. in the case of a slow heating up to forming temperature, and experiences therefore changes in its molecular structure. This type of damage can be avoided by heating at a very fast rate.

- Oxidation is caused by too high preheating temperatures and the presence of atmospheric oxygen. This damage becomes evident due to the darkening of the laminate surface. The influence of the exposure to heat was investigated by means of short beam bending tests (ILSS measurements). The specimens were produced using prepregs of 0.3 mm thickness, which had been exposed to heat prior to consolidation. The results showed no loss of strength in a GF/PA 6 after an exposure of 7 min at 240°C and a reduction of 9% after 7 min at 280°C, as compared to material made from prepregs which have not been exposed to heat.

Figure 4 shows the temperature of the laminate from the beginning of the heating in a circulating-air oven to the demoulding of the formed part. The temperature of the oven was 400°C. After 64 seconds, the 260°C hot laminate was removed and transferred within 5 seconds to the forming station. During this transfer the laminate cooled to 250°C. Immediately after transfer thermoforming took place. In a cold mould of 23°C, the demoulding temperature 110°C was reached after 4 seconds, in a hot mould of 100°C the cooling time was 20 seconds.

Figure 5. Laminate temperature during heating, transferring and thermoforming, laminate 2 mm GF/PA12, oven temperature 400°C

The whole cycle time of 74 seconds -heating, transfer, thermoforming in a cold mould and demoulding- could be reduced by shortening the heating time of 64 seconds, which takes the largest part of the cycle time. This can be done by increasing the oven temperature or, in the case of IR-heaters, the heater temperature. However, care must be taken to ensure that the time in the heating station is not exceeded, for example by malfunction in the forming station. Otherwise, the laminate temperature will get too high and the matrix will eventually be damaged.

5.1 Determination of Heating Time

Figure 6. Determination of heating time, laminate 2.2 mm GF/PA12

Starting from a given forming temperature and the known transfer time from the heating to the forming equipment, the temperature decrease during transfer can be defined and from that the temperature the laminate should have when removed from the heating.

The heating time can be defined by help of a diagram, calculated or measured, as shown in Figure 6: For an oven temperature of 390°C and a laminate temperature of 260°C the required heating time is 68 seconds.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The paper has shown that short heating times can be realised in thermoplastic laminates with contactless heating systems. This is achieved in a circulating-air oven or with IR-heaters by using heater temperatures above the required laminate temperature, but below the temperature of thermal damage in the polymer matrix. A short heating time prevents thermal damage of the laminate due to an overexposure to heat. Heating rates and heating times in the process can be calculated. Because of their thermal capacities the thermoplastic laminates may be transferred to the mould. By reducing the heating time in this way the total processing time for a thermoformed component is considerably reduced, thus enhancing the economic efficiency of thermoplastic composites.

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References:

- 1 Marissen, R., et.al., *Processing of Continuous Fibre Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites for Multi-Purpose Engineering*, Verbundwerk Wiesbaden 1991
- 2 Hou, M., Friedrich, K., *Stamp Forming of Continuous Fiber/Polypropylene Composites*, ECCM 4 Stuttgart 1990
- 3 Michaeli, W., Starke, J., *Preheating of GMT by contact heat transfer - a quick, operation-safe and economic method*, Verbundwerk Wiesbaden 1992